

Dimensionality Reduction for Optimization of Radio Base Station Transmission Based on Energy Efficiency

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Abstract—Traffic volumes in radio networks have increased exponentially over the last decade. While the efficiency of these networks has also improved minimizing energy use is an important challenge in the telecommunications industry. To ensure maximum energy efficiency it is necessary for the configuration of each element in the network is optimal at all times. Minimizing the amount of data that needs to be processed in order to identify entities in the network that are operating with low energy efficiency can provide increases in the speed of detection and reductions in the processing power and data storage required for this task. This work demonstrates how techniques for calculating the marginal contribution of individual features in a dataset can be effectively used to significantly reduce the amount of data that need to be processed to detect sub-optimally configured elements in the network that may need reconfiguration.

Keywords—*artificial intelligence, machine learning, energy efficiency, telecommunications, 5G*

I. INTRODUCTION

Significant effort has focused on the optimisation of efforts to maximize energy efficiency in telecoms networks. As data volumes have increased exponentially the rate of energy usage has been maintained at a linear level due to improved efficiencies in radio technology and improved hardware design. To maintain this trend efficiencies in every aspect of the networks have to be constantly innovated and an increase in the speed of detection of inefficiently operating network elements has the potential to provide a meaningful contribution to this effort.

Large amounts of data are available to determine the current energy efficiency. The more data that needs to be processed to find the necessary result the greater the costs incurred in terms of time and processing power etc. This data must be processed frugally so that we are not using more processing power and data storage than needed to initially identify anomalies in the energy efficiency and so that this can be done in the minimum amount of time.

A model of the form

$$X_{i,1} = f(X_{i,2}, \dots, X_{i,d}) + \text{noise}_i \quad (1)$$

Can lead to poor performance if it contains many irrelevant variables [1] so it is imperative to select the correct variables and also the correct number of variables for the function to be both effective and efficient.

The purpose of the technique described in this paper is to address the ‘curse of dimensionality’ whereby high dimensional data “may cause the deterioration of many fault detection techniques because the degree of data abnormality in fault-relevant dimensions can be obscured or even masked by irrelevant attributes” [2]. It involves reducing the dimensions necessary to quickly and efficiently identify entities in the radio network with anomalous energy efficiency so that they can be further analysed to identify the cause of the inefficiencies and to decide on the relevant remedial action in terms of reconfiguration in each case. This technique could be used to generate a list of network entities highlighted for further human intervention or it could be used to generate input to a subsequent function which would examine each case in more detail for the purpose of making specific configuration changes autonomically to resolve the energy efficiency issues identified by this technique.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The latest generations of radio technology provide enhanced energy awareness and granularity of energy measurement within the various sub-elements of the radio equipment. A wide range of energy saving features such as autonomic sleep modes for cells and multiple input, multiple output (MIMO) transmitters are also available in the latest generations of radio equipment. For cost and environmental reasons it is necessary to reduce energy usage while continuing to support increasing data volumes by intelligently leveraging the energy awareness and advanced energy saving features of the latest generations of radio technology.

To better understand the various technologies used for quantifying and maximizing energy efficiency in telecoms networks, research was conducted in the areas of Telecoms Energy Efficiency, Telecoms Standards, Machine Learning and AI (Artificial Intelligence) and Explainable AI.

A. Telecoms Energy Efficiency

Initially the research into the state of the art in current telecoms networks the current trajectory of telecoms energy usage and efficiency was investigated

In [3] the authors study current and future wireless networks from the viewpoint of energy efficiency (EE) and sustainability to meet the planned network and service evolution toward, along, and beyond 5G. Quantifying the energy consumed by each base station (BS) is the starting point for the research done in that study.

In [4] The authors propose a novel anomaly detection mechanism for the events with multiple decisive primary attributes in a collaborative device–edge–cloud architecture. This technique has as a primary step the use of a regression model for the identification of primary attributes and presents results for detection accuracy and detection time of anomalies.

In [17] the authors highlight the increased energy usage of 5G radio base stations compared to 4G radio base stations. The energy usage is typically around three times greater for base stations using 5G technology across a range of load conditions.

B. 5G

In [5] the authors address the problems of 5G networks, especially those with dense small cell deployment, suffering from high energy losses under low load conditions. This study is focussed on energy efficient network planning for 5G networks and describes how energy savings of up to 25% can be achieved in the types of deployments addressed. It highlights the dynamic nature of how QoS (Quality of Service) goals should be applied by the autonomic agents controlling the network whereby the focus should be on energy efficiency during times of low traffic load, but the priority should shift to ensuring maximum throughput when traffic loads are higher. This is an example of a driver for needing an efficient mechanism to identify anomalous energy users in real-time on an ongoing basis.

In [6] the authors survey work done towards one of the key components of network analysis (i.e.) traffic prediction in the context of 5G Network Slicing. Traffic prediction becomes an important consideration for any long running anomaly detection method trying to identify energy efficiency outliers against a background of constant network reconfiguration by a collection of autonomic agents whose priorities are shifting dynamically in response to traffic conditions as posited in [5].

C. Telecoms Standards

Standards used in telecoms and the interfaces and architectural components they consist of are a key factor in formulating an energy saving technique that can be broadly applicable to the telecom domain.

It is important to identify the capability for current and emerging standards from the main telecommunication standards bodies to support the use of artificial intelligence/cognitive networks techniques such as those proposed in this paper.

European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) was one of the first standards developing organization (SDO) to put forward a standardized view on how AI/ML ought to be embedded into a telco and networking system. The ETSI reference architecture [7] defines domain intelligence services which enable decision making via technologies such as artificial intelligence and machine learning and which are responsible for driving intelligent closed-loop automation in a domain by supporting variable degrees of automated decision-making and human oversight with fully autonomous management being the final stage.

International Telecommunications Union Telecommunications Sector (ITU-T) includes a specific focus group for AI Environmental Efficiency [8] and 3rd Generation Partnership Project 3GPP has specifications for data analytics services using AI.

Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) has introduced AI/ML in the RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC) and defined an API on the A1 interface to manage AI/ML models [9].

D. Machine Learning and AI (Artificial Intelligence)

The next area of research was to examine machine learning and artificial intelligence techniques including a range of regression algorithms to determine their suitability for predictive insight into the network given the large amount of performance and configuration that modern, highly complex networks are able to provide.

In [10] the authors review work on detection of credit card frauds on highly imbalance dataset and discusses some machine learning techniques as Random Forest, Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machines (SVM), Naive Bayes, extreme gradient boost (XGBoost) and k-nearest neighbour (KNN) which are generally used by various researchers to build a model. This work also details of how various regression algorithms work and the application of machine learning to both anomaly detection and classification problems. It identifies ensemble techniques such as XGBoost and Random Forest as producing superior results to conventional algorithms.

In [11] the authors have used machine learning (ML) techniques on computational data collected from the sensors in the manufacturing unit to predict the wafer failure in the manufacturing of the semiconductors and then lower the equipment failure by enabling predictive

maintenance and thereby increasing productivity. This work also compares a number of regression algorithms with the dual goals of prediction accuracy and minimization of training time and consequent resource and energy usage.

E. Explainable AI

Explainable AI techniques were also examined. The explainability of models used to autonomically reconfigure a radio network are an important consideration as the operators of these networks can be wary of giving too much control of their systems to autonomous agents. If these autonomous agents are able to provide humanly understandable explanations of the actions that they are undertaking as opposed to operating as a 'black-box' then the adoption of efficient agents is greatly facilitated.

In [12] an efficient algorithm for computing SHAP values for piecewise linear decision trees and additive ensembles based on them was proposed. This work first examines model explainability and interpretability with particular reference to Shapley Additive Explanation values (SHAP values) which represent the average marginal contribution of a feature value across all possible coalitions. Also, in [3] the authors use SHAP values to calculate consumption shares for each service in the base station (BS) that are proportional to the marginal contribution.

Explainable AI methods are an important consideration for a dimensionality reduction technique so that the end user can have confidence that the discard of more than 99% of the input data available for making decisions on the existence of energy efficiency anomalies has been done correctly and the most representative and predictive subset of features retained. Examining the results of an explainable AI algorithm can also potentially provide insights into the interaction of various parameters and measurements in highly complex networks. Partial Dependency Plots (PDP) can be particularly useful in this regard as described in [13]

III. TECHNOLOGY OVERVIEW - 5G NETWORKS/ ENERGY EFFICIENCY

A. Present status of AI in telecom

In [14] Ericsson sets out the present status of AI in telecommunications. Current AI/ML techniques are widespread in autonomic functions in the radio access network (RAN) and core network. There is also increasing adoption in the operations and business support systems (OSS/BSS) where network performance assurance and service level agreement (SLA) management is becoming more prevalent.

Specifically in RAN management systems, AI/ML software is used to detect RAN incidents, provide optimization insights and reconfigure proposals.

B. Intelligent RAN Automation

Intelligent RAN automation replaces manual tasks with automated functionality driving down operational costs,

using intelligent machine-learning-based functionality. The goal of intelligent RAN automation is to match different automation levels, from simple scripts to advanced AI-driven, to a specific problem. Intelligent RAN Automation can successfully address ever-changing network demands and increasing complexity, through machine learning.

Intelligent RAN Automation employs a multi-solution approach to apply the most suitable form of automation to each use case as and when they are needed. This is carried out in the RAN nodes or management system.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY/ TECHNICAL ARCHITECTURE

To develop and test the technique for dimensionality reduction a simple architecture was used including a data source in parquet format, some functions for cleaning and augmenting the data, functions for running a range of regression algorithms on the data and reporting and graphing functions used to compare the results.

Each of the functions was created using Python programming language and were deployed in a Jupyter notebook environment for ease of development.

A. Input data

The data on which this research was tested is a combination of the mean values of performance data for a 24-hour period from a collection of LTE (Long Term Evolution) FDD (Frequency Division Duplex) radio cells together with a snapshot of the configuration parameters of those cells during the same period.

Once the data was cleaned there were a total of 2665 separate features which were suitable as independent variables in a regression algorithm. The dependent variable was derived from features describing power consumption and throughput in the LTE cells which were then removed from the set of input data. The derived dependent variable was created as a classification to aid in the labelling of cells with poor energy efficiency for outlier and anomaly detection purposes.

B. Regression Algorithms Compared

To find the variables that contribute most to the energy efficiency of an entity in the radio network it is initially necessary to use a regression algorithm on the entire dataset and assess its capability to accurately predict the energy efficiency of a given entity.

As a first step several different regression algorithms were tested to determine their capability to predict the energy efficiency of each cell in the input data. This step involves using all 2665 features as input.

The metric that will be used to assess the algorithms' predictive capability is the R^2 (R-squared) score. R^2 is a variance for a dependent variable that is explained by independent variables in a regression model.

The following regression algorithms were tested, Linear Regression, Logistic Regression, Random Forest

Regression, XGBoost (eXtreme Gradient Boost) Regression. The results obtained are displayed in Fig 1.

Algorithm	R2	# features
Linear Regression	-3553700.237424	2665
Logistic Regression	-0.033876	2665
Random Forest Regression	0.95751	2665
Support Vector Machine	0.097329	2665
XGBoost Regression	0.966849	2665

Fig 1 - Performance of regression algorithms.

Of the regression algorithms tested Random Forest Regression and XGBoost Regression are much better predictors of Energy Efficiency than the other algorithms.

C. Determining minimum number of features needed for prediction

Taking the two best regression algorithms identified in the previous step the next task is to determine the most important features of the input dataset. The regression algorithms' predictors provide an ordered list of feature importances which is used to sequentially reduce the list of input features while the regression and prediction is repeated.

Firstly, all input features where the calculated feature importance is not greater than zero are discarded. Then a series of tests are executed which finds the R^2 score of progressively smaller numbers of input features in the range [500,400,300,200,100,50,40,30,20,10,5,2]. The results are plotted on a logarithmic scale below for better visual representation.

Accuracy of Random Forest Regression

Fig 2 - Accuracy of random forest regression.

Accuracy of XGBoost Regression

Fig 3 - Accuracy of xgboost regression.

The performance of the regression algorithms improves dramatically as more features are added and begins to plateau above 20 features. This represents a greater than 99% reduction in the dimensionality of the initial data.

D. Explainability of results

As an additional step and to provide reassurance of the results achieved in the previous steps an Explainable AI algorithm was applied to the reduced feature set to demonstrate how each of the important features contribute to predicting the target 'energy efficiency' feature and to aid interpretability of the choice to reduce the feature set in this way. The SHAP values were calculated for these data using the reduced feature set from the XGBoost algorithm and a waterfall plot is produced. The waterfall plot is designed to visually display how the SHAP values (evidence) of each feature move the model output from our prior expectation under the background data distribution, to the final model prediction given the evidence of all the features. [15]

Fig 4 - SHAP Waterfall plot for XGB reduced feature set.

In the figure above $E[f(x)]$ is the expected value of the target variable from the mean of all predictions.

Fig 5 - SHAP BeeSwarm plot for XGB reduced feature set.

An interesting feature of the beeswarm plot is that it gives an indication of the linearity of the relationship between features and the model output. Where red and blue values are heavily concentrated on the positive or negative side of the SHAP value axis this can indicate a linear relationship whereas red and blue values making both positive and negative contribution to the model output could indicate a non-linear relationship between the feature and the output.

To further investigate the linearity of the relationship between features and the model output a partial dependency plot can be used to plot the feature value versus the SHAP value for each sample of an individual feature.

Fig 6 - Partial Dependency Plot for pmPdcpVolDIDrb.

Fig 7 - Partial Dependency Plot for totalCMTP.

These plots show a moderately clear relationship between the features and the SHAP values which is as expected for the two features with the highest marginal contribution to the output. An interesting insight is visible in [Fig 7] where cells with 40W of transmission capacity are clearly less energy efficient than those with 60W capacity.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper sets out how regression-based techniques supported by explainable AI methods can be combined to effectively reduce the dimensionality of the data needed to make initial assessments of energy efficiency anomalies in a telecommunications network.

A notable conclusion from the above results is that the regression algorithms can be seen to have relied heavily on a small number of input features to predict the target 'energy efficiency' variable. The least important four features included in the model appear from the SHAP explainability plots to contribute very little marginally to the feature value.

These features are included in the highest contributors to the model accuracy and at a point where model accuracy still appears to be increasing (slightly) from adding more features [Fig 3] but the explainability techniques are not able to demonstrate their contribution to that accuracy through the SHAP explainer method.

It has been widely noted in the telecommunications industry that there is a need for real-time alerts regarding anomalous energy usage and energy management capabilities [16]. Identifying anomalies in energy usage which are resolvable and not just the consequence of necessarily high utilisation is an essential task for ensuring that communications are maximally efficient. Recognising the limitations of the big data, high dimensionality approach to assessing real-time energy usage measurements as anomalies means that the processing and data movement costs associated with calculating efficiency based on thousands of input features can be greatly mitigated and very efficient ways to quickly identify and resolve issues of low energy efficiency in the radio network can be widely deployed at a very low cost. These methods of efficient detection also mean that the resolution to the anomalous energy usage can be applied more quickly thereby further increasing the energy saving when compared to methods that would take longer to execute due to a dependency on larger amounts of input data and lengthier, more complex calculations.

In [17] with reference to 5G radio base stations the authors describe the building process of the energy consumption model, and then compare the difference between the traditional energy consumption model and the machine learning energy consumption model. This paper highlights the increased energy usage of 5G telecom equipment compared to 4G equipment (typically x3 greater under most load conditions) and explores the possibilities of using reinforcement learning to maximise energy efficiency as an alternative to regression-based methods. A future expansion of the method described in this paper could examine the efficacy of various sizes of dimensionally reduced data sets when using alternative methods of modelling energy efficiency using reinforcement learning or deep learning methods and compare this to the results achieved by the regression model.

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REFERENCES

- [1] David Donoho, "High-dimensional data analysis: the curses and blessings of dimensionality" Department of Statistics, Stanford University, pp. 20–21, August 2000
- [2] Zhang L, Lin J, Karim R. Sliding window-based fault detection from high-dimensional data streams. *IEEE Trans Syst Man Cybern Syst.* 2017;47(2):289–303
- [3] M. Masoudi et al., "Green mobile networks for 5G and beyond," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 107270-107299, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2932777.
- [4] J. Tang, L. Wei, W. Liu, Z. Zhou and J. Gu, "Correlation Anomaly Detection With Multiple Primary Attributes in Collaborative Device–Edge–Cloud Network," in *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 4922-4936, 15 March 15, 2023, doi: 10.1109/JIOT.2022.3221086.
- [5] O. Kochan, M. Beshley, H. Beshley and M. Levkiv, "The Technique of Modelling and Statistical Analysis of Energy Consumption in 5G Multi-Tier Radio Access Networks," 2023 17th International Conference on the Experience of Designing and Application of CAD Systems (CADSM), Jaroslaw, Poland, 2023, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/CADSM58174.2023.10076531.
- [6] D. Kulkarni, M. Venkatesan and A. V. Kulkarni, "Traffic Prediction with Network Slicing in 5G: A Survey," 2023 Third International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Smart Energy (ICAIS), Coimbatore, India, 2023, pp. 1360-1365, doi: 10.1109/ICAIS56108.2023.10073876.
- [7] Zero-touch network and Service Management (ZSM); Reference Architecture https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gs/ZSM/001_099/002/01.01.01_60/gs_ZSM002v010101p.pdf pp. 34-35
- [8] Focus Group on Environmental Efficiency for Artificial Intelligence and other Emerging Technologies (FG-AI4EE) www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/focusgroups/ai4ee
- [9] M. Polese, L. Bonati, S. D'Oro, S. Basagni and T. Melodia, "Understanding O-RAN: Architecture, Interfaces, Algorithms, Security, and Research Challenges," in *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, doi: 10.1109/COMST.2023.3239220.
- [10] A. N. Ahmed and R. Saini, "A Survey on Detection of Fraudulent Credit Card Transactions Using Machine Learning Algorithms," 2023 3rd International Conference on Intelligent Communication and Computational Techniques (ICCT), Jaipur, India, 2023, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/ICCT56969.2023.10076122.
- [11] D. Pradeep, B. V. Vardhan, S. Raiak, I. Muniraj, K. Elumalai and S. Chinnadurai, "Optimal Predictive Maintenance Technique for Manufacturing Semiconductors using Machine Learning," 2023 3rd International Conference on Intelligent Communication and Computational Techniques (ICCT), Jaipur, India, 2023, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/ICCT56969.2023.10075658.
- [12] A. Guryanov, "Efficient Computation of SHAP Values for Piecewise-Linear Decision Trees," 2021 International Conference on Information Technology and Nanotechnology (ITNT), Samara, Russian Federation, 2021, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/ITNT52450.2021.9649051.
- [13] Gupta, M, "Understanding Partial Dependence Plots (PDPs)", 2022, <https://medium.com/data-science-in-your-pocket/understanding-partial-dependence-plots-pdps-415346b7e7f1>
- [14] Ericsson, "Accelerating the adoption of AI in programmable 5G networks" 2021, <https://www.ericsson.com/4a3998/assets/local/reports-papers/white-papers/08172020-accelerating-the-adoption-of-ai-in-programmable-5g-networks-whitepaper.pdf>
- [15] SHAP documentation, 2023, <https://shap.readthedocs.io/en/latest>
- [16] Why the telecoms industry needs an energy aware OSS, 2023, <https://inform.tmforum.org/features-and-opinion/why-the-industry-needs-an-energy-aware-oss/>
- [17] H. Li, B. Chen, J. Liang, B. Shen and C. Shen, "Application of Energy Consumption Model and Energy Conservation Technology in New Infrastructure," 2022 IEEE 5th Advanced Information Management, Communicates, Electronic and Automation Control Conference (IMCEC), Chongqing, China, 2022, pp. 1638-1644, doi: 10.1109/IMCEC55388.2022.10020056.
- [18] BeGREEN: SNS-JU 2022 Phase 1 Project, <https://www.sns-begreen.com/>